

Contemporary surgical approaches for the closure of maxillary sinus defects with clinical cases from the authors' practice

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Summary

Maxillary sinus defects present a significant challenge in oral and maxillofacial surgery, particularly in cases associated with trauma, infection, or oncological resection. This article aims to provide a comprehensive overview of current surgical techniques for the closure of maxillary sinus defects and to highlight their clinical applicability through selected case presentations. Different reconstructive techniques are reviewed, including local and regional flaps, bone substitute materials combined with biomembranes, and microvascular composite flaps. Each approach has specific indications depending on defect characteristics and patient-related factors. The article includes clinical images from the archive of the surgeons at the Department of Otorhinolaryngology of Dr. Georgi Stranski University Hospital in Pleven. A satisfactory management of maxillary sinus defects requires an individualized approach and appropriate technique selection. Contemporary surgical methods offer reliable outcomes and contribute to improved patients' quality of life.

Key words: Biomaterial, bone substitutes, flaps, maxillary sinus, maxillary sinus defects, oroantral communications

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Introduction

The use of autogenous bone for the surgical closure of maxillary sinus defects is considered the gold standard in oral rehabilitation in patients with severe maxillary atrophy due to its excellent bone regeneration properties, as it possesses indisputable qualitative characteristics: osteogenesis, osteoinduction, and osteoconduction (Cardoso et al. 2016). Unfortunately, it is not always a viable option due to the limitations or morbidity associated with grafting techniques (Esposito et al. 2010). This drawback has led to the development of effective and efficient bone substitutes, with the selection of the most appropriate biomaterial being a labor-intensive process due to the great diversity available (Guan and Davies 2004). Four main characteristics are considered ideal in bone regeneration, which a bone substitute should possess (Zijderveld et al. 2009): osteogenesis, osteoconductivity, osteoinductivity, and osseointegration (Laurencin et al. 2006).

Maxillary sinus defects represent a significant surgical challenge, especially when resulting from osteomyelitis, trauma, or oncological resection (Iyer and Thankappan 2014). They are relatively rare. When they occur after extraction or trauma of an upper molar, they usually heal without complications if treated properly (Campbell et al. 2004; Bell 2008). However, when such defects arise secondarily due to osteomyelitis of the maxilla or following surgical removal of malignant tumors, the outcomes are often less favorable (Drew 2018). Even after multiple interventions, persistent oroantral communications may remain.

Oroantral communications (OAC) and fistulas (OAF) represent a pathological connection between the oral cavity and the maxillary sinus, most commonly occurring as a complication following surgical interventions in the posterior regions of the maxilla. In the absence of timely and adequate treatment, these defects may persist and lead to inflammatory changes in the sinus (Khandelwal and Hajira 2017; Azzouzi et al. 2022). These complications most frequently arise during the extraction of antral teeth, most commonly upper molars and premolars, with the main cause being the anatomical proximity or projection of the roots into the maxillary sinus (Hassan et al. 2012; Kwon et al. 2020). Interventions for cystic or tumorous pathologies or following trauma may lead to the creation of an oral-sinus communication (Chekaraou et al. 2021). Other factors leading to oroantral communications and fistulas include trauma or fractures of the maxillary tuberosity, infections of the upper molars, improperly placed or displaced implants, the presence of cysts or tumors, osteoradionecrosis, flap necrosis, dehiscence after failed implantation procedures, as well as complications following surgical interventions such as Caldwell-Luc (Ogunsalu 2005; Scattarella et al. 2010; Isler et al. 2011; Dipalma et al. 2025).

Materials and methods

We conducted a comprehensive literature review across the following databases: PubMed, Scopus, and Elsevier, covering the period from 1982 to 2025. The search strategy incorporated keywords such as “maxillary sinus,” “maxillary sinus defects,” “oroantral communications,” “bone grafting,” and “orbital facial fractures.” In addition to the literature review, selected clinical cases from the archive of the Department of Otorhinolaryngology at University Hospital “Dr. Georgi Stranski” – Pleven were included to illustrate the practical application of the described surgical techniques. Clinical cases were selected based on their relevance and representativeness of different reconstructive approaches.

Techniques for closure of maxillary sinus defects

Rehrmann method

The most commonly applied approach for the closure of oroantral communications is the vestibular mucoperiosteal flap, originally described by Rehrmann (Dym and Wolf 2012; Demetoglu et al. 2018; Konate et al. 2021). Literature data indicate that this method provides stable and reliable results, with recurrences more frequently associated with the presence of active sinus infection or non-compliance with patient recommendations (Kavrakirov et al. 1998). When infection is controlled, the technique demonstrates a minimal rate of reopening

of the communication (von Wowern 1982; Borgonovo et al. 2012). Some authors note that the approach allows extension of the flap to cover the defect, which requires careful manipulation of the periosteum at the base of the pedicle (Park et al. 2011). Furthermore, the presence of sinus infection necessitates prior medical treatment, including antimicrobial therapy and appropriate local care such as the use of decongestant nasal drops and irrigation through the perforation (Levine and Spivakovsky 2017; Chinnaiah et al. 2023). The consensus in the literature is that the Rehrmann method represents a reliable surgical option for the treatment of OAC. However, its success depends on the local tissue condition and the individual characteristics of the patient (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Clinical case from the Department of Otorhinolaryngology of Dr. Georgi Stranski University Hospital in Pleven, illustrating the application of the Rehrmann technique for closure of oroantral communications using a vestibular mucoperiosteal flap.

Palatal flap

Another method for closure of OAC is the palatal flap, which is recommended for larger perforations, defects located close to the palate, or when vestibular tissues are insufficient or compromised by previous inflammatory processes (el-Hakim and el-Fakharany 1999; Anavi et al. 2003; Er et al. 2013; Jamali 2014). According to the available literature, this approach is usually performed in an inpatient setting due to the potential risk of profuse bleeding (Hassani et al. 2016). The effectiveness of the technique depends on precise design and proper shaping of the flap, taking into account the limited elasticity of the palatal mucosa. This technique requires careful measurement and adaptation to the local tissues to ensure reliable coverage of the defect (Fatani et al. 2023; Shah and Davies 2024) (Fig. 2).

The methods described above can also be applied in upper jaw cyst surgery – with or without involvement of the maxillary sinus (Chemli et al. 2012; Safadi et al. 2020).

Bone substitute materials and biomembrane

The application of bone substitute materials for filling maxillary sinus defects after perforations or during surgery for cysts communicating with the sinus is increasingly integrated as an adjunct to flap surgical techniques (Kim et al. 2014; Shahbazi et al. 2021; Molnár et al. 2022). In addition to improving

Figure 2. Clinical case from the Department of Otorhinolaryngology of Dr. Georgi Stranski University Hospital in Pleven, illustrating the application of the Shipkov and Hassani technique with a palatal mucoperiosteal flap for closure of defects of the maxillary sinus wall.

protection against infections, this approach stimulates and accelerates bone regeneration not only in the area of the oroantral communication but also throughout the alveolar region, which is particularly important in planned rehabilitation with dental implants. Similar results have been reported in bone augmentation using a natural collagen membrane or a retrieved bony wall to close the surgical window (Molnár et al. 2022). Collagen membranes are routinely used to prevent migration of the graft material into the sinus and the oral cavity (Sikavitsas et al. 2001; Ebrahimi 2017; Zhao et al. 2021; Mirdad 2024). In larger communications, the particulate material may be replaced with shaped blocks that fit tightly to the defect and are covered with an appropriate flap, ensuring stable integration and better protection (Khan et al. 2005; Calori et al. 2011; Sbricoli et al. 2020). In this way, the combined approach using bone substitute materials and collagen membranes offers significant advantages for subsequent alveolar reconstruction and optimal preparation for dental implantology (Ahmed and Askar 2011; Cardín et al. 2024) (Figs 3, 4).

A technique for elevation of the sinus membrane has been developed to restore bone volume in the region of the maxillary sinus without damaging the membrane itself. Over the years, it has been established as a procedure with high predictability and a low complication rate (Davies et al. 2010). In contemporary practice, various types of bone grafts are used for reconstruction

Figure 3. Clinical case from the Department of Otorhinolaryngology of Dr. Georgi Stranski University Hospital in Pleven, demonstrating the use of bone substitute materials in combination with collagen biomembranes for closure of an oroantral communication and support of alveolar bone regeneration. Observations include the condition of the operative site on the 6th postoperative day.

Figure 4. Clinical case from the Department of Otorhinolaryngology of Dr. Georgi Stranski University Hospital in Pleven, showing the use of bone substitute materials in combination with collagen biomembranes for closure of an oroantral communication and support of alveolar bone regeneration. Observations on the 6th postoperative day are presented.

of atrophic maxillae, including autogenous, homogeneous, heterogeneous, and synthetic biomaterials (Guan and Davies 2004). The ideal bone substitute should provide a sufficient quantity of material, a safe donor site, no risk of disease transmission, high osteogenic activity, immediate stability, ease of handling, an appropriate life cycle, and affordable cost (Eppley et al. 2005).

Types of maxillary sinus defects

Caused by trauma

Traumatic defects of the sinus wall can be effectively and aesthetically reconstructed through surgical interventions, even in cases of significant soft tissue lacerations or comminuted fractures requiring partial bone removal (Lofgren et al. 2023). Despite the existing damage, the local tissues are often sufficient for primary and definitive coverage of the defect (Banica et al. 2013). Small, freely movable bone fragments without periosteal attachment are usually excised. At the same time, larger segments are stabilized by osteosynthesis in the closest possible anatomical position. Even significant defects of the anterior or lateral wall of the maxillary sinus usually heal without complications, provided that the key structural supports – the piriform aperture, the alveolar ridge, and the superior sinus wall – remain intact (Regev et al. 1995; Scattarella et al. 2010; Takaoka et al. 2013).

An exception is represented by defects involving the superior wall of the maxillary sinus, which also forms the floor of the orbit. In these cases, miniplates or titanium meshes are usually used in order to prevent orbital prolapse, reposition herniated orbital tissues, and stabilize compressed bone fragments (Degala et al. 2012; Yi et al. 2012). According to Tabrizi et al. (2024), titanium meshes provide secure structural support and facilitate functional recovery (Fig. 5). Precise assessment of the position of the eyeball and ocular motility is performed both preoperatively and during postoperative follow-up by ophthalmologists. In recent years, the treatment of severe orbital trauma has been carried out in a multidisciplinary context, with ophthalmologists actively participating not only in the preoperative assessment but also during the surgical procedure itself, including shaping and fixation of plates and meshes. Literature data show that this integrated approach significantly reduces the incidence of postoperative ophthalmological complications, including diplopia, enophthalmos, and sensory deficits in the region of the infraorbital nerve.

Figure 5. Clinical case from the Department of Otorhinolaryngology of Dr. Georgi Stranski University Hospital in Pleven, illustrating surgical stabilization of orbital floor and maxillary sinus wall defects through the application of titanium mesh and silicone plates following traumatic injury.

In the presence of a displaced fracture or bone defect of the superior wall of the maxillary sinus, which simultaneously forms the floor of the orbit, a differentiated surgical approach is required. In such situations, fixation with miniplates or meshes is frequently applied. In many cases, close collaboration with an ophthalmologist is carried out in order to prevent orbital prolapse, reposition prolapsed orbital tissues into the sinus, and restore bone fragments compromising the eyeball or periorbital structures (Emodi et al. 2018). Ophthalmological expertise is essential for the precise evaluation of the position and mobility of the eyeball, both in the preoperative and postoperative periods. Literature data emphasize that the treatment of severe orbital trauma should be performed within a multidisciplinary team, including mandatory preoperative consultation, intraoperative participation during modeling and placement of fixation structures, and subsequent monitoring for ophthalmological complications. The application of this approach is associated with a significant reduction in the incidence of complications such as diplopia, enophthalmos, and sensory disturbances in areas innervated by the infraorbital nerve (Burnstine 2003; Runci et al. 2017).

Necrosis and malignant diseases

In the presence of necrosis and inflammatory processes, most commonly in the form of medication-related osteonecrosis of the jaws, surgical closure of defects often demonstrates limited effectiveness (Otto et al. 2018). As noted by Kornblith et al. (1996), the severely compromised condition of the tissues, the difficulty in distinguishing between viable and necrotic bone, as well as the high risk of reactivation and recurrence, significantly limit the possibilities for successful surgical treatment. In these cases, the use of bone substitute materials is also considered contraindicated. Literature data indicate that multiple surgical interventions are often required, which may initially lead to a satisfactory clinical result after removal of macroscopically necrotic tissue. However, recurrence occurs within several months. Therefore, fabrication of an obturator prosthesis is recommended as an initial therapeutic approach, and an attempt at surgical closure should be undertaken only after complete control of the infectious process (Ta et al. 2025) (Fig. 6). When necrosis develops as a result of radiotherapy or chemotherapy for malignant tumors of the jaws, differentiation from tumor recurrence may be difficult. Therefore, in such situations, a biopsy is recommended before planning a more extensive surgical intervention.

Figure 6. Clinical case from the Department of Otorhinolaryngology of Dr. Georgi Stranski University Hospital in Pleven, illustrating medication-related osteonecrosis of the jaw and subsequent surgical closure with a vestibular mucoperiosteal flap.

Resections of the maxilla or maxillary sinus due to malignant tumors present similar reconstructive challenges. Partial and subtotal maxillectomies result in extensive defects that are often difficult to restore using local tissues (Wells and Luce 1995; Brown et al. 2000). The literature reports successful closure of such defects using an extensive mucoperiosteal flap from the hard palate, elevated on a single vascular pedicle, with good healing of the donor site. Available data indicate that the entire mucosa of the hard palate can be mobilized on a single vascular pedicle from the palatine vessels, and the donor area epithelializes without significant complications. As stated by Arana-Fernández et al. (2023), this method provides reliable coverage and adequate vascularization.

Temporal muscle flaps represent an alternative reconstructive option, although with potential aesthetic complications, including temporal depression or zygomatic prominence. According to Pathak et al. (2013), resection of the zygomatic arch (with or without subsequent osteosynthesis) may improve flap mobility and blood supply while reducing tension and the risk of complications. It should be noted that flaps placed under tension, as well as the administration of postoperative radiotherapy, significantly increase the risk of dehiscence, recurrence, and development of trismus (Fig. 7).

Other regional flaps, such as buccal, nasolabial, and platysma muscle flaps, are used relatively less frequently, despite their good blood supply and relatively easy elevation. Their main limitations are related to their small volume, thin structure, often short vascular pedicles, and increased tendency toward dehiscence. Additionally, their transfer to the inferior wall of the maxillary sinus is practically impossible in the presence of teeth. Larger regional composite flaps, such as pectoral, scapular, and latissimus dorsi flaps, are also rarely applied. Although they provide sufficient soft tissue volume and the possibility of including a bone component, their use is limited due to excessive tissue bulk, the risk of dehiscence under the influence of gravity, long pedicles, increased technical requirements, prolonged operative time, and difficulties in transfer through the soft tissues of the cheek. Also, these flaps may lead to aesthetic and/or functional compromise and hinder postoperative monitoring for tumor recurrence due to the massive tissue coverage.

Figure 7. Clinical case from the Department of Otorhinolaryngology of Dr. Georgi Stranski University Hospital in Pleven, illustrating tumor resection with clear margins and reconstruction using regional mucoperiosteal and temporal flaps.

Microvascular composite free flaps, including flaps from the iliac crest, rectus abdominis, and, more rarely, fibular flaps, represent an advanced reconstructive option in extensive maxillary defects. As noted by Iyer and Thankappan (2014), these techniques allow precise adaptation of both soft tissue and bone components to the individual defect. However, their application is limited by prolonged operative time, the need for specialized microsurgical expertise, the requirement for specific equipment, and the involvement of two or more surgical teams, as well as by the extended postoperative recovery period. Despite these limitations, data from Bulgarian authors demonstrate encouraging results. Yanev et al. (2021) and Romansky et al. (2018) report consistently high survival rates of microvascular flaps in Bulgaria – over 90%, reflecting significant progress in the field. Through the use of composite flaps and microsurgical anastomosis, defects of varying size and localization can be reliably reconstructed, positioning this approach as the gold standard not only for maxillary sinus defects but also for complex reconstructions in the maxillofacial region.

In perspective, the implementation of 3D printing technologies creates opportunities for the development of individualized bone and soft tissue substitutes, precisely adapted to the specific defect and integrating into the surrounding tissues with minimal risk of complications. This approach is described in detail by Yanev (Yanev et al. 2021) in a clinical algorithm for virtual planning, modeling, and 3D printing in local, regional, and microvascular reconstruction of complex maxillofacial defects.

Discussion

In selecting an approach for the treatment of an oroantral communication (OAC), several key factors are considered, including the size of the fistulous tract, the time since diagnosis, and the presence of sinus infection (Visscher et al. 2010). Closure is usually recommended within 48 hours of onset in order to reduce the risk of additional complications. If direct suturing of the defect is insufficient, the use of a flap is considered as an alternative surgical

approach (Parvini et al. 2018). Prior to performing closure, adequate control of sinus infection is necessary to prevent exacerbation (Kwon et al. 2020). According to Wassmund (1939), the development of sinusitis is observed in 60% of cases by the fourth day after sinus exposure, while other authors report a sinusitis rate of 50% by the third day after administration of oral anticoagulants (Watzak et al. 2005). Therefore, early and confirmatory diagnosis is essential for successful closure of OAC. In situations involving larger defects or in patients with a history of sinus disease, surgical closure is recommended as the initial method (Haas et al. 2003). The timing of intervention remains critical, and treatment should be carried out as soon as possible after the occurrence of the communication in order to optimize the outcome and reduce postoperative complications.

The choice for OAC closure technique is determined by the localization and size of the defect, the planned prosthetic treatment, and the surgeon's experience (Yalcin et al. 2011). Unilateral odontogenic sinus infection is controlled through drainage and elimination of the odontogenic cause. Additionally, the choice of bone grafting method is determined by the goals of subsequent rehabilitation, including placement of a dental implant. Furthermore, in evaluating OAC in relation to adjacent teeth, consideration is given to the height of the alveolar ridge, the duration of the defect, the presence of sinus inflammation, and the patient's general health status (Guyen 1998).

Conclusion

The surgical treatment of maxillary sinus defects remains a complex and technically challenging procedure in reconstructive surgery. Although results are sometimes not entirely optimal, the variety of available reconstructive methods provides effective options tailored to the etiology, size, and localization of the defect. With careful case selection, precise surgical execution, and comprehensive postoperative care, durable closure of the defect and significant improvement in the patient's quality of life can be achieved. The choice between the classical Rehrmann method and the use of bone substitute materials with biomembranes depends primarily on whether the patient plans future implant placement and on the size of the defect. In bone grafting, the main advantage is restoration of the bone structure, as they serve as a scaffold for new bone and prevent collapse of the alveolar ridge. Their use, especially in combination with less invasive flaps, allows closure of the defect with minimal tension on the tissues, thereby preserving the normal anatomy and depth of the oral cavity.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declare that informed consent was obtained from the patients participating in the study at the Dr. Georgi Stranksy University Hospital in Pleven.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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